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AWARENESS OF E LEARNING AMONG RURAL PEOPLE OF KERALA

Reshma S¹, Soumya Eappan ², Sr. Juli A D³

^{1,3}, Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce, Carmel College Mala, Kerala, India

² Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce St. Xavier's college for Women Aluva, Kerala, India

Abstract

The life of knowledge and human skills today is shorter than ever, mounting the pressure to remain up to date with ones education and training throughout a career. In the age of globalization and technological revolution, four-year degrees are just the start of a forty-year continuing education. Life-long learning is quickly becoming an imperative in today's world. E-Learning is referred to as teaching and learning by using electronic media. The use of network technology to design, deliver, select, administer, and extend learning. This methodology supports the use of networking and communications technology in teaching and learning. E-Learning is generally meant for remote learning or distance learning, but can also be used in face-to-face mode. In this paper focused to study about the awareness of E-Learning in selected rural areas in India, the influential factors as well as restricted reasons also evaluated. This study is Descriptive nature. Convenience sampling method used and mainly depend on structured questionnaire to collect the primary data.

Key words: E-Learning, media, rural-area

Introduction:

Electronic learning or E-Learning is a general term used to refer to a form of learning in which the tutor and student are separated by space or time where the gap between the two is bridged through the use of online technologies. E-Learning applications and processes include computer-based, web-based, technology based learning and virtual education opportunities. Content delivery is with the help of Internet, intranet, extranet, audio or video tape, satellite TV, and CD-ROM and it includes media in the form of text, image, animation, streaming video and audio. It allows us to learn at our own way i.e. on our own time with a flexible, interactive and engaging online experience. In this

process, educational activities can be accomplished by using networking and communications technology in online or offline, synchronous as well as asynchronous, networked or standalone teaching and learning. People have started using Internet for accessing information via Internet. The corporate sector which was providing distance education has also taking place using online learning as an added activity in their distance education because E-Learning is a way of getting better the accessibility of the study material, moreover, the cost of accessing information online is decreasing by the advancement in the field of information and communication technology. Students and teachers are increasingly using accessing information online to support their learning and teaching. Now a days, the trend is of “blended learning”, that is learning is a combination of traditional learning as well as E-Learning.

Following are the features identified of E-Learning: Learning is centered around the interests of the learner. Learning is immersive learning by doing and takes place not in a school but in an appropriate environment. Therefore, “blended learning” provides us an interest and an appropriate environment to teaching learning process. The main attribute of E-Learning is the flexibility of accessing information and resources. It refers to the access the use of information and resources at any time, place or pace according to one’s convenience. Learner is not bound with the constraints of attending the lectures on fixed time or fixed location which may be far off from the residence. Another attribute is access of multimedia based resources; it means that different type of media like text, audio, video, animation, graphics, picture is supported by the network and communication technology, which makes possible the accessing of information by not only text or pictures but it also supports animations, videos, presentations, audio etc. which makes learning more interesting and valuable. Moreover the information and communication technology provides us an opportunity to capture, store, and distribute information in the form of text, pictures and illustrations which includes multimedia-based simulations of simple and complex processes which are cheaply accessible. Asynchronous Methods Embedded learning: Embedded learning is information that is accessible on a self-help basis, 24/7. It can be delivered to the place of work, or to mobile learners. Electronic performance support system (EPSS) is a type of embedded learning. The advantage is that embedded learning offers learners the information they need whenever they need it.

Courses: The clear advantage of a self-paced course is convenience. Participants can get the training they need at any time. This can include just-in-time training where a participant gets exactly the training he or she needs to perform a task.

Discussion groups: A discussion group is a gathering of conversations that occur over time. They are also called message boards, bulletin boards and discussion forums. Discussion groups can be used to support a group of participants taking the same class or can be used to support participants performing related tasks. A discussion group is a very proficient way to supply expert answers to a large group people. A single answer to a common question can help many.

Synchronous Methods Virtual classroom: Virtual classroom duplicates the features of a real classroom online. Participants interact with each other and instructor online, instant messaging, chat, audio and video conferencing etc.

Blended Method: Most companies prefer to use a mix of both synchronous and asynchronous e-learning methods according to their requirement

Significance of the study:

In the E world everything goes to 'E' terms. Without education we cannot reach the highest point. So in the recent trend e learning plays a vital role. Everyone can learn without the limitation of cost, time, geographical boundaries, age, gender etc. E learning provides equal opportunities for the accusers, but the exploitation of the opportunity depends on them each. It can be utilized by diversified manner.

Today single teaching learning method is not effective. As traditional method has an advantage of how to teach or learn though E-Learning provides us the latest methods and statistics.

The popularity of E Learning to the rural area may be very slow due to the lack of sufficient infrastructural facilities like network connection, unawareness of this programmes etc. While this study can find out the reasons to restrict the usage, and the influencing factors to use e learning technique.

Scope of the study:

Now in the modern age the entire activities changed due to widespread internet technology. Everything changed to online mode. In the educational field also contribute wide spread learning conveniences through network system. E learning is also effective method to teaching and learning process. In the recent scenario E learning provides wide opportunities which helps to achieve high degrees with low cast and time. Material source is enormously available on online access.

The scope of this study is to evaluate the awareness of e learning programme among rural people. There by understand the factors influencing adopt the e learning methods as well as the main reasons to restrict the adoption of e learning.

Literature review:

Shiva Kanaujia et al. (1999), discussed about the benefits of E-Learning and also suggested that E-education is not a new concept in India but has grown the importance with the growth of Internet. He also discussed the advantages of E-Learning mainly, the best information can be accessed from the place where it was originally created. The students can access the information across the world from their homes' only, which was a main constraint for those who cannot afford the opportunities due to the lack of financial aids or assistance. The impact and new challenges of E-Learning for the students and instructors are described by authors in.

Alyne Rothberg et. al.(2000) has suggested organizational strategies for accessing E-Learning opportunities with having the availability of the broadband connection. They also discussed the Government assistance in expanding

broadband. Rural areas and people face a number of issues when it comes to access to and adoption of broadband. The issues include availability, cost, and lack of technical skill and knowledge. The largest discrepancy in the reasons between rural and urban residents not having home internet is lack of access. He further recommended that access to broadband and online learning is a key element to prepare students and employees for the future. A strong correlation exists between broadband access and educational attainment, employment opportunities, and individual and community-wide economic viability.

Nilay M.Yajnik (2000) had discussed about the Next Generation Internet, in which usage of the Internet is growing tremendously but restricting the applications like Virtual Reality to be made available for distance learning purpose without higher bandwidth. Next Generation Internet is the area of Digital Libraries which requires improved quality of services such as continuous digital video and audio. Author also discusses that Natural Language Interface, is a way by which humans can communicate with the machine in a language that is natural to them. It is in nascent stage today but has tremendous potential for rural areas. Rural based NGO's which are working for rural development could build such training applications directly without needing to wait for the IT industry to develop applications for them.

Dr. T. Rama Devi (2001) presented initiation of National Institute of Rural Development (NIRD) using ICT tools for the training of persons involved in rural development programs of central and state governments. Success of ELearning will only come with clear and well-defined instructional objectives, through preparation of content and an infrastructure, which offer support for both participation and instructions. NIRD is conducting about 180 training programmes in a calendar year. If they adopt E-Learning technologies in their training programmes it would be cost-effective.

Objectives:

1. To identify the influencing factors for the adoption of E-learning by the rural people.
2. To find out the reason for restricted usage of E-learning among rural people.

Research Methodology:

This study Awareness of E learning among rural people in Kerala is descriptive in nature and makes use of a descriptive research design. Both primary and secondary data are used for this study. Primary data is collected through survey. Secondary data were collected from website, books, journals etc. Primary data was collected from sample of 200 rural people in Kerala.

In the present study a structured presented questionnaire was used as the tool to collect data from the selected rural people. The first part of the questionnaire contains questions on personal profile which includes age, gender, marital status, income and occupation. The second section contains question related to measurement of awareness and usage of e-learning services. The third section contains question related to the influencing factors for the adoption of e-learning services and the reason for the restricted use of e-learning services.

Confirmatory Factor Analysis, AMOS 18.0, Structural Equation Model, Chi-Square Test , Multiple Regression Analysis are the main statistical tools used for this study.

Data Analysis And Interpretation:

Main objective of this study is to identify the influencing factors for the adoption of E-learning by the rural people. That is use full SEM to test the following hypothesis

H₁: Convenience is an influential factor to for the adoption of E- learning services by the rural people.

H₂: Ease of Use is an influential factor to for the adoption of E- learning services by the rural people

H₃: Time saver is an influential factor to for the adoption of E- learning services by the rural people

H₄: Access of wide resource material is an influential factor to for the adoption of E- learning services by the rural people

H₅: Efficiency is an influential factor to for the adoption of E- learning services by the rural people

H₆: Economical Aspects is an influential factor to for the adoption of E- learning services by the rural people

H₇: Availability of foreign tutors is an influential factor to for the adoption of E- learning services by the rural people

Model fit Indices for CFA Influencing factors for adoption of E- learning services

	χ^2	DF	P	Normed χ^2	GFI	AGFI	NFI	TLI	CFI	RMR	RMSEA
Influencing factors	12.559	5	.028	2.520	.988	.888	.997	.985	.998	.014	.103

(source: survey data)

All the attributes loaded significantly on the latent constructs. The value of the fit indices indicates a reasonable fit of the measurement model with data.

Table 4.34 Regression coefficient

Path	Estimate	CR	P	Variance explained
Convenience -> Influencing factors	0.953	26.155	<0.001	90.8
Ease of Use ->Influencing factors	0.859	18.099	<0.001	86.2
Time saver -> Influencing factors	0.886	19.692	<0.001	97.3
Access of wide resource material -> Influencing factors	0.973	30.117	<0.001	94.7
Efficiency-> Influencing factors	0.987	35.296	<0.001	78.5
Economic Aspects-> Influencing factors	0.929	23.173	<0.001	73.8
Availability of foreign tutors -> Influencing factors	0.988	35.861	<0.001	90.8

(source: survey data)

Next objective of the study is to find out the reason for restricted usage of E-learning among rural people.

H₁: Network connection problem in rural area is the reason for restricted usage of E- learning service by the rural people

H₂: Discomfort ability is the reason for restricted usage of E- learning service by the rural people

H₃: Language problem is the reason for restricted usage of E- learning service by the rural people.

H₄: Lack of computer/network knowledge is the reason for restricted usage of E- learning service by the rural people. `

H₅: Lack of infrastructure facility is the reason for restricted usage of E- learning service by the rural people `

H₆: Inaccessibility is the reason for restricted usage of E- learning service by the rural people.

H₇: Lack of human touch is the reason for restricted usage of E- learning service by the rural people

H₈: Lack of training is the reason for restricted usage of E- learning service by the rural people

Table 4.35 Model fit Indices for CFA Restricted use of E banking services

	χ^2	DF	P	Normed χ^2	GFI	AGFI	NFI	TLI	CFI	RMR	RMSEA
Restricted use	11.549	11	.399	1.050	.986	.955	.976	.997	.999	.077	.016

(source: survey data)

All the attributes loaded significantly on the latent constructs. The value of the fit indices indicates a reasonable fit of the measurement model with data.

Table 4.36 Regression coefficient

Path	Estimate	CR	P	Variance explained
Network connection problem ->Reason for RU	0.724	12.857	<0.001	52.4
Discomfort ability->Reason for RU	0.542	8.519	<0.001	29.3
Language problem ->Reason for RU	0.361	5.306	<0.001	13.0
Lack of computer/network knowledge->Reason for RU	0.758	13.916	<0.001	57.4
Lack of infrastructure ->Reason for RU	0.358	5.258	<0.001	12.8
Inaccessibility ->Reason for RU	0.177	2.511	0.013	3.1
Lack of human touch ->Reason for RU	0.362	5.322	<0.001	13.1
Lack of training ->Reason for RU	0.707	12.368	<0.001	50.0

(source: survey data)

FINDINGS:

To identify the influencing factors for the adoption of E- learning services by the rural people.

1. Convenience is an influential factor to for the adoption of E- learning services by the rural people.
2. Ease of use is an influential factor to for the adoption of E- learning services by the rural people.
3. Time saver is an influential factor to for the adoption of E- learning services by the rural people.
4. Access of wide resource material is an influential factor to for the adoption of E- learning services by the rural people.
5. Efficiency is an influential factor to for the adoption of E- learning services by the rural people.
6. An economic aspect is an influential factor to for the adoption of E- learning services by the rural people.
7. Availability of foreign tutor is an influential factor to for the adoption of E- learning services by the rural people.

To find out the reason for restricted usage of E- learning service among rural people.

1. Network connection problem is the reason for restricted usage of E- learning service by the rural people.
2. Discomfort ability is the reason for restricted usage of E- learning service by the rural people.

3. Language problem is not a reason for restricted usage of E- learning service by the rural people.
4. Lack of computer/network knowledge is the reason for restricted usage of E- learning service by the rural people.
5. Lack of infrastructural facility is not a reason for restricted usage of E- learning service by the rural people.
6. Inaccessibility is not a reason for restricted usage of E- learning service by the rural people.
7. Lack of human touch is not a reason for restricted usage of E- learning service by the rural people.
8. Lack of training is the reason for restricted usage of E- learning service by the rural people.

Conclusion:

There are several technologies available to enable distance learning today. Two such emerging technologies which have great potential for E learning in Rural India are The Next Generation Internet and Natural Language Interfaces. Both these technologies are still at a very early stage both in India as well as abroad, however, our Industry and policymakers can take advantage of these technologies and utilise them for the benefit of the rural masses of India. E-Learning is found to be highly emerging knowledge tool today. It has wide span in developed as well as in developing countries. The areas which are undeveloped and not so educated get attraction of ELearning. E-Learning provides a method of delivering knowledgeable stuffing through CD, DVD, multimedia and other tools. The main constraints to access the E-learning facility among rural people are network problems, discomfort ability, lack of technical knowledge etc. There are number of influencing factors to adopt the e learning mechanism too, they are Convenience, Ease of use, Time saver, wide availability of resource materials etc.

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